

DEFORMATION BEHAVIOR AT VERY HIGH STRAIN RATES IN A 17 VOL % SiC/ZK60 COMPOSITE

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ABSTRACT

The effects of strain rate on the strength and ductility of a 17 vol% SiCp reinforced ZK60 (Mg-6%Zn-0.5%Zr by weight) composite were investigated by dynamic and quasi-static tests. Dynamic tests in the strain rate range up to 4000 s^{-1} were performed using a modified split Hopkinson pressure bar system, whereas quasi-static tests in the strain rate range below 10^{-1} s^{-1} were carried out with an Instron machine. The maximum strength measured at the dynamic strain rate (10^3 s^{-1}) is about 500 MPa, but it is only 460 MPa at the quasi-static strain rate (10^{-3} s^{-1}). The total elongation at the dynamic strain rate (approximately 1.5 %) is, however, almost the same as that at the quasi-static strain rate. The fracture surfaces of samples tested at both strain rates were also examined in order to correlate with the differences in mechanical property.

INTRODUCTION

A number of magnesium alloys have been shown to exhibit excellent mechanical properties, such as high specific strength at room temperature and superplasticity at moderate temperatures [1-3]. Recent advances in manufacturing technology further resulted in the development of magnesium-base composites. Because of their high specific modulus and strength, these composites have great potential to be used for aerospace structures. In order to be used for structural components, it is necessary to characterize the mechanical properties of these composites. However, very limited data are currently available for magnesium-base composites under dynamic loading. The purpose of this work is therefore to investigate the mechanical properties of a magnesium-base composite at a dynamic strain rate of 10^3 s^{-1} . To make a comparison, the mechanical properties of the unreinforced matrix alloy were also characterized.

MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTS

The composite used in the present study is a 17vol% SiC particulate-reinforced ZK60 magnesium composite (ASTM designation: ZK60/SiC/17p). The chemical composition of the matrix is Mg-6%Zn-0.5%Zr by weight. The material was received as an extruded rod. Figure 1 shows the microstructure of the composite. Transmission electron micrograph, as shown in Fig. 2(a), indicates that the material contains equiaxed fine grains with an average size of about 0.3 - 0.5 μm . SiC particles were irregular and have an average size of approximately 2 μm . As a result of the fine-grained structure, the composite has been reported to be superplastic at a very high strain rate ($> 1 \text{ s}^{-1}$) [4].

The unreinforced matrix alloy (Mg-6wt%Zn-0.5wt%Zr) was prepared as a direct-chill cast ingot by Mitsui Kinzoku Corp. To obtain a fine-grained structure, the ingot was extruded at 583K with

Figure 1. Microstructure of the composite.

Figure 2. Microstructure of (a) the composite and (b) the unreinforced matrix alloy.

a reduction ratio of 100:1 and, then, annealed at 573 K for 7.2 ks. Microstructures of the annealed alloy is shown in Fig. 2(b). The alloy contained equiaxed fine grains with an average size of about $2 \mu\text{m}$. A large amount of second phase precipitates are also noted to distribute along grain boundaries.

Tensile specimens, machined directly from the extruded bars, have their tensile axes parallel to the extrusion direction. The gauge length of the specimen is 5.0 mm, and the diameter is 2.5 mm. Tensile tests at the quasi-static strain rate (10^{-3} s^{-1}) and dynamic tensile tests (10^3 s^{-1}) were performed using an Instron machine and a modified Hopkinson pressure bar, respectively. All tests were carried out at room temperature. A schematic diagram of the modified Hopkinson bar apparatus with the measuring system is shown in Fig. 3.

Figure 3. A schematic diagram of the modified Hopkinson bar apparatus with the measuring system.

Flow stress σ_s , strain rate $\dot{\epsilon}_s$, and strain ϵ , in the specimen during the dynamic tensile test are calculated from the following equations:

$$\sigma_s = E \cdot \left(\frac{A}{A_s} \right) \cdot \epsilon_T \quad (1)$$

$$\dot{\epsilon}_s = \frac{2c_0}{a} (\epsilon_I - \epsilon_T) \quad (2)$$

$$\epsilon_s = \frac{2c_0}{a} \int_0^t (\epsilon_I - \epsilon_T) dt \quad (3)$$

where $\epsilon_I + \epsilon_R = \epsilon_T$ is assumed; ϵ_I is the incident strain pulse, ϵ_R the reflected strain pulse, and ϵ_T the transmitted strain pulse; ϵ_I and ϵ_R are detected from a strain gage attached on the input bar, and ϵ_T is measured using a strain gage attached on the output bar; A and A_s are the cross sectional area of the output bar and the specimen respectively; E is the Young's modulus of the output bar; c_0 is the velocity of the elastic wave along the output bar; a is the gage length of the test specimen; and t is time.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

STRESS-STRAIN RELATION

The engineering stress-strain curves for ZK60/SiC/17p and Mg-6Zn-0.5Zr at strain rates of 10^{-3} and 10^3 s^{-1} are shown in Fig 4. Bold lines are results from samples tested at the dynamic strain rate (10^3 s^{-1}), and plain lines are at the quasi-static strain rate (10^{-3} s^{-1}), respectively. It is readily observed that the higher the strain rate the higher the flow stress. At both strain rates, the Mg-6Zn-0.5Zr alloy shows a large plastic deformation region and followed by necking. In the case of ZK60/SiC/17p, on the other hand, samples fractured at an early stage of plastic deformation without necking. Apparently, the presence of SiC particles greatly constrains the plastic deformation of the alloy matrix.

Figure 4. The engineering stress-strain curves for ZK60/SiC/17p and Mg-6Zn-0.5Zr

STRENGTH

The 0.2% proof stresses of ZK60/SiC/17p at both strain rates of 10^{-3} and 10^3 s^{-1} are presented in Fig. 5. For comparison, the 0.2% proof stresses of pure magnesium deformed at the same strain rates are also included in Fig. 5 [5]. It is readily observed that the additions of Zn and Zr, and SiCp to Mg matrix can all improve the proof stress. In the case of alloying, stress increment is attributed to solid solution strengthening and grain refinement. In the case of composite, there is an additional strength enhancement resulting from compositing. The ultimate tensile strengths (UTS) of both alloy and composite samples tested at 10^{-3} and 10^3 s^{-1} are presented in Fig. 6. In a manner similar to the proof stress, UTS increases with the additions of Zn and Zr, and SiCp reinforcement. Also noted in Figs. 5 and 6 is the result that, in general, testing at the dynamic strain rate produce higher proof stress and UTS than testing at the quasi-static strain rate.

Figure 5. The 0.2% proof stresses of samples tested and pure magnesium[5] at the strain rates of 10^{-3} and 10^3 s^{-1} .

Figure 6. The ultimate tensile strengths (UTS) of samples tested and pure magnesium[5] at the strain rates of 10^{-3} and 10^3 s^{-1} .

DUCTILITY

The total elongation of samples tested at the strain rates of 10^{-3} and 10^3 s^{-1} is shown in Fig. 7. Data obtained from pure magnesium deformed at the same strain rates are included in this figure [5]. The elongation value is noted to increase remarkably with the alloying of Zn and Zr at both strain rates. In contrast, total elongation decreases in the composite. In the case of alloying, elongation increase may be attributed to a finer grain size in the alloy as compared to that in pure Mg. It may also be a result of different textures developed in the two materials, since Mg is hexagonal whose mechanical properties (e.g., strength and ductility) are expected to be sensitive to crystallographic texture. In the case of composite, however, elongation decrease is attributed to the preferential microcrack formation at matrix/reinforcement interfaces.

In general, total elongation at the dynamic strain rate is smaller than that at the quasi-static strain rate for all test samples. This trend appears to be associated with a change in the fracture mode. For example, in Mg and Mg-6Zn-0.5Zr, it was found that fracture at quasi-static strain rate resulted from the development of microcracks within the grains. In contrast, fracture at dynamic strain rate resulted from the development of microcracks near grain boundaries [5]. Further study is needed to identify the cause.

Figure 7. The total elongation of samples tested and pure magnesium[5] at the strain rates of 10^{-3} and 10^3 s^{-1} .

FRACTURE

Figures. 8(a) and (b) show typical fracture surfaces of Mg-6Zn-0.5Zr and ZK60/SiC/17p deformed at 10^3 s^{-1} , respectively. The fracture surface of Mg-6Zn-0.5Zr consists of spherical, ductile dimples much larger than the average grain size ($2\ \mu m$). Fracture seems to occur by the nucleation and growth of voids at the second phase/matrix interfaces. On the other hand, the fracture surface of ZK60/SiC/17p consists of small spherical voids with a size similar to that of reinforcement ($2\ \mu m$). This suggests that plastic deformation in the composite is highly localized. In other words, the matrix is highly constrained by the presence of SiC reinforcement; this leads to stress localization and, thus, the premature failure.

SPECIFIC STRENGTH

The specific tensile strength of samples examined at both strain rates of 10^3 s^{-1} and 10^{-3} s^{-1} is shown in Fig. 9. To make a comparison, data from some lightweight alloys, including the conventional 7075 Al-T6, AZ61 Mg-F, AZ80A Mg-T5, Mg-10%Al-3%Zn-3%Mn-6%Si (by mass%) [6], and rapidly-solidified (RS) EA65-RS (Mg-5.1Al-4.9Zn-6.7Y, by mass%) Mg alloy [7], are also included. It is pointed out that data for these alloys were measured at quasi-static strain rate ($\sim 10^{-3}$ s^{-1}). The specific strength of ZK60/SiC/17p is noted to be higher than that of Mg-6Zn-0.5Zr at both strain rates. In addition, ZK60/SiC/17p at the quasi-static strain rate exhibits a higher specific strength than the conventional alloys. However, it is similar to the RS alloys. While the two RS alloys still have a 15 - 20 % elongation, ZK60/SiC/17p shows only limited ductility. It needs to point out that one of the major benefits of using composite is its high specific modulus (stiffness).

Figure 8. Typical fracture surfaces of (a) Mg-6Zn-0.5Zr and (b) ZK60/SiC/17p.

Figure 9. The specific tensile strength of samples examined at both strain rates of 10^3 s^{-1} and 10^{-3} s^{-1} with data from some lightweight alloys [6, 7].

SUMMARY

Several conclusions can be drawn from the present study:

1. The 0.2% proof stress and ultimate tensile strength of ZK60/SiC/17p composite are higher at 10^3 s^{-1} strain rate is higher than those deformed at 10^{-3} s^{-1} .
2. The total elongation of ZK60/SiC/17p deformed at 10^3 s^{-1} is slightly smaller than that at 10^{-3} s^{-1} .
3. Fracture surface revealed that the low ductility of ZK60/SiC/17p is caused by void development and growth at the reinforcement/matrix interfaces.

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